

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

CHEMISTRY IN THE ENVIRONMENT

Hrytsuliak Halyna,

PhD., Associate Professor

Student, Ivano-Frankivsk National Technical University of Oil and Gas

Fedorko Natalia,

Teacher,

*Ivano-Frankivsk Vocational College of the
Lviv National University of Nature Management*

Mindyuk Vasyl

Student,

Ivano-Frankivsk National Technical University of Oil and Gas

Abstract

"Environmental Chemistry" highlights the relevance and importance of the study and analysis of chemicals that affect the environment. The work covers a variety of analytical chemistry techniques that are used to identify and quantify chemical pollutants in water, air, and soil. Special attention is paid to modern techniques, such as chromatography, mass spectrometry, and their implementation for environmental safety monitoring. These emphasize the importance of developing new analytical methods capable of detecting low concentrations of toxic substances, which is key to timely response to environmental threats and environmental protection.

Keywords: pollution, agriculture, environment, chemistry

Analytical chemistry of the environment and agricultural products is a branch of chemistry that studies the composition and properties of various substances in natural and agricultural environments. Various analytical methods such as chromatography, mass spectrometry, spectroscopy, and electrochemical methods are used to determine the composition and concentration of various substances. For example, pesticides, heavy metals, antibiotics, and other contaminants in food, soil, water, air, and other environments are analyzed. These data help manufacturers, consumers and quality control authorities understand the level of safety and quality of products and take the necessary measures to preserve the cleanliness of the environment and public health. The goal of research in the field of analytical chemistry of environmental and agricultural products is to ensure human safety. The main task of such studies is the monitoring of environmental pollution by various sources of pollution, such as industrial emissions, agricultural waste, municipal waste, water and soil pollution. Analytical chemistry allows the detection and measurement of a wide range of pollutants, including heavy metals, organic compounds, pesticides, herbicides and other toxic substances. Assessment of the impact of agricultural production on the environment

Research on the impact of the use of pesticides, herbicides, fertilizers and other chemicals in agriculture on soil quality, water resources and biodiversity. Analytical methods make it possible to detect chemical residues in soil, water, plants and food products and to assess the risks to human health and ecosystems. Food Safety: examines the chemical composition and safety

of foods such as vegetables, fruits, grains, and animal products. The analysis includes measurements of pesticides, herbicides, antibiotics, heavy metals and other toxic substances, as well as beneficial components such as vitamins, minerals and antioxidants. Based on the results of the analyses, recommendations and strategies will be developed aimed at reducing environmental pollution and risks to public health by implementing more environmentally friendly methods of agricultural production and waste management. In addition, the effectiveness of measures to manage risks and promote sustainable development will be monitored: One of the main goals of this research is to identify new compounds that may be harmful to human health and the environment.

Assessment of the effectiveness and safety of chemicals: the analysis of chemicals used in agriculture and industry in order to assess their effectiveness and potential danger to humans and the environment: based on the results of the analysis, the risk of disease and other adverse health effects is assessed due to exposure to chemicals in the environment and food. Support for the development of new technologies and methods: The results of research in the field of analytical chemistry can be used to develop new technologies and methods for cleaning the environment and improving methods of agricultural production that minimize the negative impact on the environment: Analysis of the impact of climate change on the environment and the chemical composition of agricultural products - another direction of research.

Fig. 1. depicts the analysis of various chemicals used in agriculture and industry.

An analysis of a variety of chemicals used in agriculture and industry, focusing on their effectiveness and potential hazards to both humans and the environment. The image includes laboratory settings with scientists as well as diagrams and charts that represent chemical structures and their effects.

Here is an illustration with a detailed analysis of chemicals used in agriculture and industry. This image focuses on their effectiveness and potential hazards to humans and the environment. You can see scientists analyzing chemical samples in a laboratory setting, along with data charts and environmental images that highlight environmental issues.

Identifying the relationship between climate change and environmental pollution can help in the development of adaptation and mitigation measures. Analytical chemical studies of the resistance of microorganisms also include the analysis of the resistance of microorganisms to antibiotics and other chemicals used in agriculture. Evaluating the effectiveness of environmental protection measures Analytical chemistry can evaluate the effectiveness of environmental protection measures taken to reduce pollution of the environment and agricultural products. This includes analyzing the effectiveness of water, soil and air treatment technologies, as well as monitoring the use and disposal of chemicals: an important aspect of research is the research and development of new analytical methods that

can more accurately and efficiently measure the chemical composition of the environment and agricultural products. This includes the development of new sensors, chromatography, spectroscopy and other innovative technologies. Promotion of international cooperation: Research in the field of environmental and agricultural analytical chemistry is international in nature and promotes cooperation between countries in solving common problems such as environmental pollution and food safety.

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